

Computational study into the experimental capabilities of the MTRR SCW reactor^{*}

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Abstract

Two stages of the MTRR-SCW reactor operation are planned: a test stage and a research stage. This paper considers the research stage of the MTRR-SCW experimental reactor operation, the purpose of which is to investigate current and advanced light-water reactors. The MTRR-SCW driver-type core provides a fast neutron spectrum with the possibility for the local warmup in ampoule devices and independent loop channels. Irradiation channels will be installed in the core center and periphery, as well as instead of the reactor's changeable reflector cartridges. The MTRR-SCW irradiation channels and independent loops will provide ample opportunities both for undertaking a research on effects from neutron irradiation of different materials, and for testing a variety of fuel assembly designs and operating conditions (temperature, pressure, neutron spectrum), as well as for investigating transients and emergency processes. The MTRR-SCW channels can be used to irradiate different types of fuel, and structural and absorbing materials with different coolant inlet temperatures (from 250 to 450 °C) and, consequently, its inlet density (from 800 to 100 kg/m³ respectively), providing different neutron spectrum options for the experimental fuel assembly in a range from thermal to fast spectrum. The MTRR-SCW allows experiments to increase power and simulate emergency processes, including reactivity accidents (RIA). The strong primary and safeguard vessels of the independent loop channels also make it possible to simulate loss-of-pressure emergencies of the LB LOCA and SB LOCA types. The peripheral independent loop channel will allow undertaking experiments for simulation of alternative reactor concepts with reactors with SKD coolant parameters, such as a single-circuit concept with the pseudophase transition in the core (VVER-SKD-1700), and with natural coolant circulation in the core (SKDI). In addition, the peripheral channel allows accelerated irradiation of fuel rods used in current VVER reactors, taking into account the reproduction of the ratio between damaging dose and burnup rates.

Keywords

VVER-SKD, MTRR-SCW, light-water reactor, supercritical coolant parameters, test reactor, research reactor

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Introduction

As part of the 2019-2028 R&D Subprogram “Development of Technologies for the Pressure Tank Power Reactor with Supercritical Coolant Parameters (VVER-SKD)”, National Research Center “Kurchatov Institute”, in collaboration with co-contractors, has developed a concept of a nuclear power plant (NPP) based on the VVER-SKD power reactor with a fast neutron spectrum and light-water coolant with supercritical parameters (Alekseev et al. 2023). The MTRR-SCW multipurpose test research reactor concept has been proposed to provide experimental support for the reactor development and design effort (Sedov et al. 2023).

Due to the lack of a reference for operation of reactor plants with supercritical water coolant, the MTRR-SCW reactor will be operated at the initial stage of investigations as an experimental reactor. As defined in GOST 23082-78. Nuclear reactors. Terms and definitions, an experimental reactor is a nuclear reactor designed to be used as a test facility for obtaining data on reactor physics and technology required to design and develop reactors of this type or their components.

After the initial stage goals and objectives are achieved concerning the test demonstration of the reactor plant and NPP physical processes and special technologies and equipment (Lapin et al. 2025), the MTRR-SCW will operate as a research reactor at stage 2. Its key function for that stage will be to irradiate items in the supercritical light-water coolant environment (fuel rods, samples of structural materials, targets, etc.), as well as to simulate transients and emergencies in independent leak-tight MTRR-SCW reactor loops (reactor rise to operating parameters, maneuvering modes, reactor shutdown, power surges, coolant pressure decrease and relief modes, reactivity accidents, etc.).

This paper deals with the research stage of the MTRR-SCW operation and considers the experimental capabilities of the reactor for addressing issues relating to different SKD reactor concepts and the light-water reactors in operation.

Specific features of the research reactor loop channels

There is a successful experience in operating loop channels in different research reactors.

Two conceptually different types of loop channels were used in the MR multi-loop material testing reactor: one with once-through circulation and the other with a Field-type layout (Bat et al. 1985; Alekseev et al. 2019). Specific to the reactor is that the channel itself and all service lines are installed in the cold water pool, which requires properly insulated high-temperature circuits. Loops using water as coolant are equipped with a system of filters for entrapping the circuit corrosion products and nuclear fuel fission products.

The MR reactor loops had a broad range of research applications. Of interest for the SKD effort are:

- exploration of thermal load effects on the fuel rod performance;
- fuel rod endurance testing up to high burnup values under different water chemistry conditions;
- structural material testing.

There is a well-known design of a Field-type loop channel for fuel rod testing in the MIR.M1 nuclear research reactor (Boehmert et al. 1989), which comprises the coaxially arranged vacuum jacket, channel shroud and coolant flow divider, with fuel rods to be tested accommodated inside of it. The MIR.M1 reactor is designed to test experimental fuel elements, FAs and structural materials for nuclear plants for multiple applications (transport, power) operating with different loads in various environments (gas, water, liquid metals, organic compounds). In terms of physical peculiarities, the reactor is a pressure-tube reactor and, likewise the MR reactor, is installed in a pool with water.

Multiple experimental devices for nuclear fuel testing have been developed in the MIR.M1 reactor. The following irradiation devices are of interest for the SKD reactors (Buruikin et al. 2008):

- demountable devices for fuel rod testing in step-rate and cyclic power change modes using movable screens or fuel rods;
- instrumented devices for testing single fuel rod and FA parts with simulation of design-basis loss-of-coolant accidents (LOCA);
- instrumented devices for testing with simulation of the design-basis positive reactivity insertion accident (RIA) conditions;
- devices for leaky fuel rod behavior investigations;
- devices for testing structural materials and components of water-cooled reactor FAs.

The SM research reactor is a tank-type high-flux reactor with an intermediate neutron spectrum and pressurized water used as coolant. The SM reactor is equipped with an extensive range of experimental devices, including two loop facilities: a low-temperature loop facility (VP-1) and a high-temperature loop facility (VP-3) (Tsykanov et al. 2007; Starkov et al. 2013; Sereдкин et al. 2020; Izhutov et al. 2022). The VP-1 loop facility is designed to test experimental fuel rods, irradiate samples of structural and absorbing materials, and produce isotopes. The VP-3 loop facility is designed to test service ability of fuel rods for different types of reactors, explore the escape of fission products from leaky fuel rods and techniques for their removal from the primary circuit, and test structural and absorbing materials.

For the SM reactor, a power change in any channel is associated with the power change in the reactor as a whole, and, for some channels, with the CPS rod repositioning. The SM reactor power change cannot be therefore used for control in all cases, specifically in the event of a power increase to above the specified level in the given reactor cycle. An (upward) fuel content selection error for one or more channels leads so to a decrease in the irradiation parameters in other channels and to a smaller operating efficiency of the SM reactor as a whole.

Thus, steady-state processes are or can be implemented in the SM loop devices, concerned for the most part with investigations of structural material properties and radionuclide production.

The Jules Horowitz reactor, France, deserves special attention. Specific to this reactor is that it uses a fuel irradiation loop circuit called ADELIN (an advanced device for experiments with nuclear fuel rods irradiated to as great extent as possible) designed specifically to investigate fuel rod behavior in the course of power rise transients. The ADELIN device will implement different types of power rises in a range from slow to high rates and from low to very high power changes using different fuel types. The key feature of the test device is that it provides well-defined ramp tests, which make it possible to determine the fuel rod failure thresholds (Gaillot et al. 2016).

This fuel irradiation circuit consists of two parts: one accommodated in the reactor pool inside the core, and the other installed in the experimentation zone. The in-core part includes an irradiation device, submerged pipelines, and liquid and electrical connections through the pool test penetrations. The off-core part consists of a liquid circuit, a leak-tight hopper, and the circuit connection to the reactor service lines. The liquid circuit is equipped with a circulation pump for the cooling water circulation towards the device and achieve the required thermal hydraulic conditions at the test channel inlet (270 °C, 200 g/s).

There are also movable devices capable of moving the irradiated structure towards or off the core center, which allows simulation of reactivity accidents and other dynamic processes. Deserving no less attention are irradiation devices, in which it is possible to test fuel rods for failures, investigate radiation-induced corrosion, transmute minor actinides, and test materials for advanced reactors in high temperature and neutron flux conditions (Console Camprini et al. 2016).

There is currently a MBIR research reactor with a fast neutron spectrum (Dragunov et al. 2012, 2013) under construction in Russia. The reactor design version has 20 irradiation channels, including one seven-cell central loop channel (CPC), two peripheral loop channels, 14 instrumented channels, and three cells for radionuclide production assemblies. Specific to the initial stage of the MBIR reactor operation is absence of technically complex loop channels. These facilities will not be probably yet ready for operation in the initial period, but the cells for these channels must be filled. Of special importance in this sense is the central loop channel that occupies seven cells in the core center. It is not reasonable to use all these cells for irradiation assemblies because of a major effect they have on each other. To avoid this effect, three additional irradiation assemblies and four standard FAs are proposed to be accommodated in the CLC cells.

Central loop channel (CLC)

The MTRR-SCW's central loop channel at the level of the core's fuel part comprises the cylindrical shroud of the loop channel, in which a cylindrical irradiation device (ID) is installed. Helium circulates between the ID housing and the loop channel shroud to make up for the

pressure difference and cool the ID housing. The ID internal space can accommodate different items. Up to seven standardly spaced fuel rods can be accommodated in such channel (Fig. 1). The coolant circulation inside the ID is of the Field type (downward coolant flow in the peripheral annular channel and upward flow in the fuel rod bundle).

Figure 1. Design of the MTRR-SCW central loop channel.

Justifying the reactor safety in conditions of a loss-of-coolant accident (LOCA) or the high-density coolant entry into the core requires experimental simulation of such emergency processes. To confirm that it is possible to experimentally simulate accidents and transients in the central loop channel, suggesting that the coolant density changes, the neutron flux density and linear load distribution was calculated for the fuel rods installed in the reactor core in the immediate vicinity of the loop channel and in the loop channel itself for fuel with a plutonium content of 22% and uranium enrichment of 0.1 or 20% with different coolant densities.

Noteworthy, with the space inside the central channel around the test fuel rods (with a uranium content 0.1 or 20%) being flooded by coolant with a density of 1 g/cm³, the power density in the core driver fuel rods adjoining the loop channel grows respectively by 12% and 13%. And the maximum linear load in the loop channel as such grows by more than twice (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Linear load distribution along the CLC fuel rod height for different loop coolant flow densities, the uranium enrichment in experimental fuel rods being **a.** 0.1%; **b.** 20%.

Experimental simulation of emergences and transients requires that power density values in excess of those for standard fuel are achieved in experimental fuel rods installed in the central loop channel (CLC). Due to the fact that the maximum linear load in the VVER-SKD power reactor is at the level of 300 W/cm, and a linear load of only 211 W/cm can be achieved in the loop channel irradiation device with standard plutonium and depleted uranium contents (the same as in the MTRR-SCW and VVER-SKD fuel), increasing the power density requires increasing the concentration of fissile materials. One of the options is to use standard MTRR-SCW fuel rods with a plutonium content of 35% or more. In this case, however, most loop channel experiments may not be representative, since the fuel's chemical composition will differ from that of the standard VVER-SKD fuel. One more option is to use enriched uranium in fuel rather than waste uranium. In this case, it will be possible to increase the linear load by increasing the content of fissile nuclides without changing the fuel's chemical properties.

By way of example, neutron flux and linear power density distributions were calculated for experimental fuel rods installed in the central loop channel. The fuel composition of experimental fuel rods consists of MOX fuel with a plutonium content of 22%, and the uranium enrichment assumes such values as 0.1%, 5%, 20%, 50%, 75% and 90%. An option with steel fuel rod simulators installed inside the loop channel was also considered to estimate its disturbances affecting the MTRR-SCW neutron flux and power density fields. The CLC axial linear power density and neutron flux distributions as a function of uranium enrichment in experimental fuel rods are shown in Figs 3, 4 respectively.

Figure 3. Linear load distribution along the CLC fuel rod height as a function of uranium enrichment in experimental fuel rods.

Figure 4. Neutron flux density distribution along the CLC height as a function of uranium enrichment in experimental fuel rods.

As can be seen from the obtained dependencies, it is possible to achieve the CLC maximum linear loads of about 900 W/cm by using fuel in experimental fuel rods with the same chemical composition as in the MTRR-SCW and VVER-SKD fuel, i.e. with a MOX fuel plutonium content of 22% and uranium enrichment of 90%. Such values will make it possible to undertake the CLC experiments with a major power increase and for a cyclic power change.

The effect of the CLC experimental fuel rod composition on the parameters of the core driver fuel rods immediately adjoining the channel was estimated. It was determined that the linear load along the core fuel rod height in the event of 90% uranium fuel used in the loop channel increases by only 2% compared to steel rods used in the channel.

The achieved power density values, the strong primary and safeguard shrouds, and a small number of test fuel rods (no more than seven) will make it possible to undertake the CLC power ramp and emergency simulation experiments, including reactivity accidents (RIA), as well as to simulate loss-of-coolant (LB LOCA and SB LOCA) accidents in the channel.

Peripheral loop channel (PLC)

Along with the VVER-SKD reactor concept with a fast resonance neutron spectrum, there are a number of conceptual proposals for light-water reactors with supercritical parameters.

- VVER-SKD-1700, a single-circuit two-loop reactor plant with direct energy conversion with a single- and two-pass core with a fast resonance neutron spectrum and a loop layout. Feedwater with a temperature of 280 °C to 320 °C is delivered to the core inlet, and superheated steam with a temperature of 540 °C and a pressure 24.5 MPa is delivered to the core outlet (Glebov et al. 2019).
- SKDI-670, a two-circuit reactor plant with natural coolant circulation, a thermal resonance neutron spectrum and an integral layout. The in-vessel steam generators produce steam for the subcritical pressure turbine. The coolant pressure in the reactor is 23.5 MPa, and the temperature is 343 °C to 395 °C (Silin et al. 2015).

There are a number of points and outstanding issues about the concepts under consideration which require individual in-pile tests. Such tests can be undertaken in the MTRR-SCW peripheral loop channel, which represents an independent channel with Field-type cooling installed on the core periphery in place of seven FAs (Fig. 5).

The peripheral loop channel makes it possible to install a large number of fuel rods, as well as the of standard MTRR-SCW FAs, expected to make experiments representative and minimize disturbances affecting the FA power density fields around the PLC.

Figure 5. Peripheral loop channel.

The PLC also allows irradiation of advanced fuel rods with different types of fuel and cladding materials in a broad range of light-water coolant parameters.

Ampoule devices (AD)

Placement of ampoule devices in the MTRR-SCW reactor makes experiments with irradiation of test fuel rods in the light-water SKD coolant environment much more representative by providing the required neutron spectrum typical of VVER-SKD reactors.

The MTRR-SCW reactor core is surrounded by six rows of reflector assemblies, which form a bundle of steel rods in a hexagonal jacket with the same width across flats as for the FA. The AD can be installed in any MTRR-SCW reflector cell. It is also possible to consider the AD accommodation immediately in the reactor core in place of one of the FAs due to a slightly smaller refueling cycle or power density.

The AD may have a contained or flow-through design depending on the conditions of the given experiment. The AD can accommodate a bundle of seven test fuel rods surrounded by a tube for dividing the downward and upward coolant flows.

Three options have been considered with the AD installed: in the reflector cell at the boundary with the core, in the reflector cell at the boundary with the partition, and in the core cell (in place of one of the FAs in row 4).

The axial distribution of the fast neutron fluence (with energy of over 0.5 MeV) and the 450-day damaging dose in the fuel cladding were estimated for the proposed options. Two types of irradiated items were considered (MOX fuel rods and steel kernel simulators).

The test fuel rod cladding in the analytical model was divided axially into 10 cm high layers. The fast neutron fluence and the damaging dose were estimated in each layer.

Calculations show that the 450-day irradiation of the AD structure under consideration is expected to lead to a fast neutron fluence of about $1.36 \cdot 10^{20}$ to $1.85 \cdot 10^{22}$ n/cm² and a damaging dose of 0.13 to 16 dpa. It needs to be noted that the MTRR-SCW is not a high-flux reactor and, therefore, the advanced damaging dose accumulation

may be hard to explore. Due to a large-size side reflector, however, this reactor will allow a large number of irradiation devices to be accommodated for a broad range of simultaneously undertaken investigations.

Experimental capabilities of the MTRR-SCW for effective light-water reactors

Since the 1980s, a vital issue has been in sufficient number of test and experimental facilities for justifying safety of the VVER reactors in operation (Makhin 2005). This is confirmed by the efforts undertaken then to build the PRIMA reactor plant for experimental simulation of design-basis and beyond-design-basis accidents. In the second half of the 1980s, due to the lack of funds, the activities in this field were stopped, so the only option for eliminating the backlog in fuel safety investigations was to use the research reactors existing in Russia. Due to their design and physical features, fuel safety investigation experiments for VVER reactors began to be conducted at the MIR.M1 reactor where they have been based since (Alekseev et al. 2013). The reactor has been however in operation since 1966, and no alternative exists nowadays to the MIR.M1 investigations (Romanovsky et al. 2018).

The MTRR-SCW reactor could extend the research scope and make the experimental data obtained more representative for justifying safety of effective light-water VVER-type reactors. The MTRR-SCW driver zone generates a fast neutron spectrum with the possibility, on the whole, of its local warmup in irradiation devices and in independent loop channels. The reactor plant loop channels can be used for a full range of experiments, including on fuel rod failures. The MTRR-SCW functionality extends the MIR.M1's experimental capabilities.

The peripheral loop channel will allow experiments with long-term irradiation of standard VVER core fuel rods in nearly realistic conditions of irradiation. The channel design makes it possible to create irradiation conditions as close to the VVER conditions as possible: coolant temperature and pressure, fuel rod pitch, fuel and cladding materials. Computational studies were undertaken which simulated a group of fuel rods installed in the VVER-1000 reactor cartridge and in the MTRR-SCW peripheral channel. A comparison was also made between the neutron spectrum formed in the VVER-1000 reactor and within the seven central fuel rods installed in the MTRR-SCW loop channel. The comparison results are presented in Fig. 6.

Despite rather a fast neutron spectrum in the MTRR-SCW core, the PLC design and physical features allow one to obtain the VVER-1000 reactor's own spectrum in it. The driver zone is the neutron source in this case.

The key criterion for viewing as representative the obtained results during long-term irradiation of experimental fuel rods in the MTRR-SCW loop channel is the proximity of the ratio between the rate of the damaging dose

accumulation on the fuel rod cladding and the fuel burnup in the fuel rod to the same parameters in the VVER reactor. The burnup and damaging dose accumulation rate was calculated for the fuel rod group irradiation in the VVER reactor (OECD NEA 2002) and in the MTRR-SCW peripheral loop channel. The results are presented in Table 1.

Figure 6. Neutron spectrum: 1 – MTRR-SCW peripheral loop channel with VVER-1000 fuel rods; 2 – VVER-1000 reactor; 3 – MTRR-SCW reactor.

Table 1. Parameters of the test fuel rod irradiation in the MTRR-SCW loop channel compared with VVER-1000 FAs

Parameter	VVER-1000	MTRR-SCW loop channel
Damaging dose accumulation rate, dpa/s	$5.35 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$7.25 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Burnup accumulation rate, (MW·day/kg)/s	$4.89 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$6.35 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Damaging dose accumulation rate, dpa/ (MW·day/kg)	$1.09 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$

Thus, as can be seen from the values obtained, the peripheral loop channel shows rather a good fit with the VVER-1000 reactor for the damaging dose and burnup accumulation rate ratios. And the absolute values of the damaging dose and burnup accumulation rates are higher in the MTRR-SCW loop channel than those for the VVER-1000 reactor, this to allow accelerated irradiation.

The central loop channel equipped with the strong primary and safeguard shrouds will make it possible to

simulate experimentally emergency processes, including loss-of-coolant and high-density coolant inflow accidents, as well as to undertake fuel rod failure experiments.

Conclusion

To achieve the objectives involved in justifying experimentally the VVER-SKD effort development, a concept is proposed for a nuclear power plant based on the MTRR-SCW reactor to be operated in two stages: a test stage and a research stage. The paper considers the MTRR-SCW's experimental capabilities during operation at the research stage.

It is possible to achieve a practically fivefold increase in power density, compared to fuel rods for standard core FAs, in the central irradiation channel of the independent reactor loop in the process of irradiating test fuel rods with 90% ^{235}U fuel enrichment. At the same time, the power density disturbance in fuel rods of the standard FAs, which surround the central irradiation channel, does not exceed 5%. This circumstance allows central channel experiments with power increase and simulation of emergency processes, including reactivity accidents (RIA). The central loop's strong and safeguard shrouds and a small number of tested fuel rods (not more than seven) make it possible to use this channel to simulate loss-of-pressure accidents (LB LOCA and SB LOCA).

The peripheral loop channel is capable to accommodate a large number of fuel rods and a standard MTRR-SCW FA, expected to produce representative experiment results and minimize the power density field disturbances in the FAs that surround the peripheral loop channel. Its experimental capabilities make it possible to simulate the coolant flow spectral characteristics and parameters for different concepts of advanced reactors, as well as for the light-water VVER-type reactors in operation.

The channel allows irradiation of advanced test fuel rods with different types of fuel and cladding materials in a broad range of light-water coolant parameters.

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